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GAMEHEARTS

State-of-the-Art Report 2

Project: Games, Heritage, Arts, & Sport: the economic, social, and cultural value of the European video game ecosystem. GAMEHEARTS

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1. Project Summary

GAMEHEARTS will seek to maximise the value of the European video game industry ecosystems (hereafter, EVGIE) within a wider social context of the creative and cultural industries (hereafter, CCI). This will consider the importance of the EVGIE in contributing to economic growth, job creation, physical and mental wellbeing, and social and cultural cohesion, by particularly focusing on how a stronger and closer working relationship between more the traditional and emergent cultural sectors, can work better to create more inclusive and socially responsible cultural experiences. The consortium will offer policy recommendations and roadmaps setting out how the EVGIE can and should develop, and where it could act as a driver for sustained innovation and economic growth. It will utilise an evidence-based approach that focuses not just on video game development, but rather adopts a holistic ecosystem approach, utilising both established and more innovative methodologies, to consider the competitiveness and development of the EVGIE, and how video game know-how and technologies could drive innovation in the wider CCI. In doing so, GAMEHEARTS will develop ‘ludic experiences’, to explore possibilities of more inclusive, engaging, and empowering cultural experiences. Working across seven work packages the universities of Salford (UK), Tampere (Finland), Vienna (Austria), Breda University of Applied Sciences (Netherlands), and Wroclaw University of Economics and Business (Poland) will work in partnership with Ubisoft (France) and other major video game partners and associations (including the VGE & EGDF) to explore current and future trends in the EVGIE. Beyond this, we will work with certain cultural case studies partners to consider the ways in which game-related technologies and practices are, and could be used to, increase access to heritage, the arts, and sport.

2. Introduction

Many technological, cultural and societal breakthroughs are increasingly focusing on understanding the impact of video games on modern economy and society, including the impact in shaping a more inclusive society. This focus aims to address the urgent call for action to promote socially sustainable environments towards enabling everyone to reach their fullest potential. However, the extent to which video games can create such imperative environments and even how game design itself can become more inclusive is still unknown, and a comprehensive investigation of the existing capacities is required to properly inform future research and development on this topic, especially towards maximising the economic, social, and cultural value of the European video game industry ecosystem – which is the main goal of GAMEHEARTS.

In the process of understanding how video games, game tools, ludic practices and any other technological, cultural, and societal development in which reality becomes more gameful (hereafter, gamification (Hamari, 2019)) can create empathic and inclusive experiences, researchers from Tampere University (Finland) consolidated the current state-of-the-art of intersection between social sustainability and gamification, more particularly on how they can support each other to promote a more equitable, diverse, and inclusive (hereafter, EDI)¹ society towards allowing better *design* (by understanding its contexts), *development* (by understanding its methods), and *evaluation* (by understanding its effects).

¹ While the authors acknowledge that some references use DEI (or similar, as DE&I) instead of EDI, this report purposefully positions Equity first, as we understand that equitable practices and policies are necessary to ensure long-lasting diversity and inclusion actions.

3. Methodology

We conducted a systematic literature review to synthesise the existing knowledge on the contexts, approaches, and impacts of gamification in relation to or based on EDI. A systematic review is a comprehensive analysis of existing literature on a certain subject, which involves summarising findings from existing studies and identifying areas where further research is needed (Kitchenham et al., 2009). For this evaluation, we adhered to the PRISMA 2020 statement (Page et al., 2021) to create a replicable protocol towards methodological rigourness and reliability, which is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PRISMA-2020 diagram.

In addressing the overall goal of this research following a reproducible process, we would like to specifically understand which meanings gamification has, which methods it employs and how it impacts EDI by defining three research questions to be answered, being:

- **RQ1:** What are the many contexts in which gamification is being used to support EDI?
- **RQ2:** What are the approaches gamification is employing to support EDI?
- **RQ3:** What types of effects does gamification have towards EDI?

Based on these research questions, our next step was to define the search keywords using the PICO tool, which focuses on understanding the population, intervention, potential comparisons, and outcomes (Methley et al., 2014). In this literature review, it was specified as follows:

- **Population:** Research focusing on social stratification, including issues such as the underrepresentation of certain groups, discrimination against minorities, stereotypes, and biases, as well as strategies to address these problems, such as those promoting equity, diversity, inclusion, justice, and fairness.
- **Intervention:** Research that designed, implemented or used gamification in relation to or based on EDI.
- **Comparison:** Not applicable, as this review does not aim to compare gamification with non-gamified approaches, nor to compare gamification approaches among themselves.
- **Outcomes:** Not applicable, as we aim to consolidate any and all of the current effects.

Through the PICO tool, it was possible to understand that our search string should comprise both keywords related to *EDI* (e.g., discrimination, stereotype, biases, diversity, inclusion, equity, justice, fairness) and to gamification itself. Therefore, the search string was extensively tested and ultimately defined as (*diverse OR diversity OR inclusive OR inclusiveness OR inclusivity OR inclusion OR equality OR equity OR minorities OR underrepresented OR discrimination OR discriminative OR discriminatory OR stereotype OR bias OR justice OR fair OR fairness*) AND

gamification. We searched for journal articles and conference papers that match this search string in their title, abstract, and keywords on studies published before 2024 in the most user search engines in these topics, being: ACM Digital Library (<https://dl.acm.org/>), IEEE Xplore Digital Library (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/>), Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com/>), and Web of Science (<https://www.webofscience.com/>). Considering studies published in 2023 or earlier, ACM returned 113 studies, IEEE Xplore returned 118 studies, Scopus returned 778 studies, and Web of Science returned 727 studies, resulting in a total of 1736 studies. From this total, 635 were identified as duplicates through Zotero (<https://www.zotero.org/>) reference management system, leaving 1101 records to be screened.

These 1101 records were individually screened by at least two researchers in order to ensure that they were: **a)** full studies (i.e., not work-in-progress or workshop calls); **b)** written in English; **c)** primary studies (i.e., not systematic reviews or meta-analyses); **d)** accessible for download through Tampere University; **e)** designing, implementing or using gamification; and **f)** addressing equity, diversity and inclusion.

After the individual screening, the first author of this document identified disagreements between peers and invited a third researcher to be an active listener or participant in the discussion towards a consensus. As a result, 64 records were not a complete study, 139 were not original, 79 were not in English, 50 were not available through Tampere University, and 418 were not tackling gamification as defined by Hamari (2019) as the intentional process of transforming any activity, system, service, product, or organisational structure into one which affords similar positive experiences, skills, and practices as found in games. Moreover, 331 were removed because they were not tackling EDI as defined by the American Psychological Association [APA] (2021) as the act of addressing, acknowledging, or rectifying historical disparities and the resulting exclusion of certain groups based on certain characteristics, such as race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, socioeconomic status, disability, age, immigrant status, and language. As a result of this screening and discussion, this literature review ended up including 20 studies, as listed in Appendix A.

The included studies were equally distributed among all reviewers involved in the screening to create a synthesis matrix, which was numerically comparing and qualitatively characterising them through an integrated design approach (Noyes et al., 2019). This matrix was later

reviewed and standardised by the first author, with the acknowledgement from all involved researchers. Regarding **contexts** (RQ1), we examined the objectives, intended audiences, and settings in which gamification is being applied as a tool to or a subject of EDI actions. Regarding **approaches** (RQ2), we collected information related to theories, game design, research nature, and data collection methods. Regarding **effects** (RQ3), we collected the measured outcomes, as well as consequences on them (e.g., increase, decrease).

4. Results

4.1 CONTEXTS (RQ1)

In terms of objectives, 10 studies concentrated on using gamification as a means to promote EDI, particularly for marginalised groups based on factors such as gender, age (including both children and older adults), sexual orientation, language, disability, and immigration status. The other 10 studies examined how to make gamification more inclusive by understanding game design preferences across various genders, age groups, and disabilities. Considering the first half of studies that were using gamification to promote EDI behaviours, their specific objectives related to:

- **Promoting gender diversity and inclusivity in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) disciplines:** Two of the included studies focused on using gamification to support gender diversity in STEM, either by introducing gender-inclusive indicators (equitable chances, fair treatment, comprehensive training and healthy work-life balance) in a technology course at University level (Garcia-Holgado et al., 2019), or by creating a gamified educational tool for parents who had limited or no exposure to STEM disciplines in developing enough skills to become positive role models for their children (Wernbacher et al., 2022), specifically discouraging parents from acting as gatekeepers for girls that would like to pursue a career in these fields.
- **Advancing linguistic diversity and equity:** Two studies focused on using gamification to support linguistic diversity, be it through encouraging Kenyan children in enhancing their Swahili reading comprehension skills (Ndegwa et al., 2023) and by motivating native speakers to generate content in South African Resource Scarce Languages, including isiNdebele, isiXhosa, isiZulu, Sepedi, Sesotho, Setswana, siSwati, Tshivenda, and Xitsonga (Von Holy et al., 2017). One study also aimed to promote linguistic equity through gamification by allowing refugee children to learn mathematics in their own native languages (Le Pichon et al., 2024).
- **Encouraging healthy behaviours among sexual minorities:** Two studies focused on creating gamified approaches to support sexual health either in the prevention or treatment. As a tool to avoid sexually transmitted diseases among men who have sex with men, a gamified application would send reminders of preventive measures (e.g., using

condoms) when they are in venues where sexual activities are likely to take place, such as gay saunas and nightclubs (Besoain et al., 2020). As a tool to support treatment of people infected with human immunodeficiency virus in undertaking antiretroviral therapy by using gamified medication reminders and social support (Hightow-Weidman et al., 2021). Still, another study did not tackle sexual health but rather focused on reducing alcohol use among Lesbian-, Bisexual-, and Queer-identified (LBQ) women who are moderate to heavy drinkers through a digital competition towards community-building to address negative stereotypes associated with this group (Boyle et al., 2022).

- **Promoting functional diversity:** Two studies focused on promoting functional diversity to underrepresented populations as well as allies through gamification, either by introducing a training program to prevent cognitive decline in older people who are at risk of developing dementia (Mora et al., 2016), or by enhancing the understanding of various disabilities and strategies to overcome their associated challenges among Early Childhood Educational degree students (Manzano-León et al., 2022).

The second half of studies were trying to understand how to create a more equitable, diverse and inclusive gamification design, especially towards:

- **Gender-specific gamification design:** Five different studies exclusively focused on understanding how gamified environments can be tailored to people's gender to some extent by following a binary approach to it (i.e., women and men). This endeavour has so far been done by evaluating the effects of gamification in women learning mathematics, especially when comparing their academic achievement when experiencing leaderboards that were either dominated by masculine or feminine names (Christy & Fox, 2014). Similarly, three studies examined the impact of a gamified environment to test logical reasoning in reinforcing gender stereotypes by using colour-coded badges (blue for men, purple for women, and grey as neutral), leaderboards with either masculine-only, feminine-only or mixed names, and avatars that were either gender-specific photos or mixed representations (Albuquerque et al., 2017; Oliveira et al., 2023; Santos et al., 2023). Finally, one last study assessed the impact of gamification as points, badges, rewards, leaderboards and progression on three semesters of a Software Analysis and Design course using gender as a moderating variable, which proved to have no difference between genders considering data from all three semesters (Codish & Ravid, 2017).

- **Age-specific gamification:** One study exclusively focused on understanding how to design gamification for older adults, especially investigating how they perceive long-term objectives, tasks' difficulty and game design when learning computer basics (Minge & Cymek, 2020).
- **Gender- and age-specific gamification:** Two studies focused on both gender and age by analysing how gamification can change girls' interest in technology (Casey et al., 2023) and by investigating the influence of gender and age on gamified civic participation in urban planning (Thiel et al., 2019).
- **Disability-specific gamification:** Two studies also exclusively focused on creating accessible gamification to people with disabilities, considering their visual and hearing needs in learning mathematics (De Souza Sombrio et al., 2016) or proposing game design guidelines to enhance the touristic experiences of people with vision impairments (Huang & Lau, 2020).

Therefore, gamification has so far been used to address and include mainly *gender*, *age*, and *disability* marginalised groups as intended audiences. Additionally, gamification was also employed to address *sexual orientation*, *language*, and *immigrant status*. Several studies have examined diverse audiences, such as by facilitating the learning of mathematics in the native language of refugee children (i.e., considering age, language, and immigrant status), or exploring ways to help parents support girls in STEM disciplines (i.e., considering gender and age), as summarised by Figure 2.

Figure 2. Included studies by their purpose and target groups.

The most prevalent setting was *education*, as summarised in Figure 3. Studies in this field focused on various subjects, including mathematics (such as numeracy, geometry, logical reasoning, algebra, and calculus) and technology (including digital literacy, future technologies and careers, software analysis, computer engineering, and cybersecurity). Additionally, gamified educational digital interfaces are used in subjects related to languages (such as Swahili) and pedagogy. In the field of healthcare, researchers have focused on addressing

sexual *health behaviours* by using gamified approaches to prevent and treat sexual diseases, but also developing training programs aimed at preventing cognitive decline in older adults and addressing psychoactive substance abuse among LBQ women. Moreover, gamification is being used to encourage civic e-participation in accessible *urban planning* and to improve the tourism experience.

Figure 3. Included studies by their application settings.

4.2 APPROACHES (RQ2)

Numerous theories have provided support for the integration of gamification and EDI, being mostly from psychology, game design, and education, either by the included theoretical and empirical studies. *Gender stereotype threat* was employed by four studies to explore its impact on individuals' experiences. Moreover, three studies associated the intersection of gamification and EDI with motivation through the *Self-Determination Theory*,¹ while two other studies focused on the flow state (i.e., the one in which a person experiences deep engagement with an activity) through the *Flow Theory*.² Three studies utilised the Mechanics, Dynamics, Aesthetics (MDA) framework³ to facilitate the gamification design, while other two studies employed project-based learning to implement their educational activities. Other theories were the basis for only one of the included studies, as shown in Table 1, whereas four studies did not make any reference to theories.

Psychology	10 studies, being:
Gender stereotype threat	4 studies
Self-determination theory	3 studies
Flow theory	2 studies
Cognitive neoassociation theory	1 study
IMB skills model	1 study
Maslow's hierarchy of needs	1 study
Nudge theory	1 study
Perma model	1 study
Science capital framework	1 study
Theory of planned behaviour	1 study
Trans-theoretical model	1 study

1 Ryan R. M., Deci E. L. (2020) Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a self-determination theory perspective. *Contemporary Educational Psychology* 61: 101860. [10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101860](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101860)

2 Csikszentmihalyi M. (2000) *Beyond Boredom and Anxiety*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.

3 Hunnicke R., LeBlanc M., Zubek R., et al. (2004) MDA: A formal approach to game design and game research. *AAAI Workshop on Challenges in Game AI* 4: 1–5.

Design	7 studies, being:
MDA framework	3 studies
Accessibility recommendations	1 study
Co-design	1 study
Goal/Question/Metric framework	1 study
Gamification design framework	1 study
Lazzaro types of fun	1 study
LeBlanc types of fun	1 study
User-centred design	1 study
Education	4 studies, being:
Project-based learning	2 studies
Problem-based learning	1 study
Universal design for learning	1 study

Table 1. Theoretical foundations employed by the included studies

All studies used achievement-based game design, in which dominance of points, badges, and leaderboards reflects the most widespread game elements in gamification.⁴ To elaborate further, *points* were provided as a reward depending on the tasks that participants needed to perform, the duration of their access to the gamified platform, and the number of friend recommendations. Participants, in certain studies, could forfeit these points due to subpar performance or gambling but, in most cases, points were the basis for *leaderboards*. *Badges* were also granted based on tasks milestones or points. Other achievement-based game elements were *challenges*, *levels*, *feedback*, *progress bars*, *goals* and *status*, which were all quantitatively focused on supporting participants in improving their performance towards the purpose of gamification (e.g., education and health).

Similar to achievement-based elements, 13 studies employed immersion-based ones, either through avatars, rewards and narratives. *Avatars* could be customised by the participants in several ways, such as using predefined photographs, uploading personal pictures, or using an avatar creator. *Rewards* were represented as digital currency for purchasing avatar customisation, virtual sweets to be collected in a basket, puzzle pieces to assemble,

⁴ Koivisto J., Hamari J. (2019) The rise of motivational information systems: a review of gamification research. *International Journal of Information Management* 45: 191–210. [10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2018.10.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2018.10.013)

segments of a song, and even monetary incentives. *Narratives* allowed participants to assume the position of a superhero in which, when engaged in a task, they would be rescuing the planet or supporting people in distress. Remarkably, there were four studies using social-based game elements as collaboration and voting, even though the nature of EDI is, as the name itself indicates, inherently social. *Collaboration* was ultimately introduced to participants as team missions or peer challenges, whereas *voting* involved responding to questions or messages authored by others. A summary of the game design elements employed can be seen in Table 2.

Achievement-based elements	20 studies, being:
Points	15 studies
Leaderboards	11 studies
Badges	9 studies
Challenges	6 studies
Levels	6 studies
Feedback	5 studies
Progress bars	4 studies
Goals	2 studies
Immersion-based elements	13 studies, being:
Avatars	8 studies
Rewards	6 studies
Narratives	3 studies
Social-based elements	4 studies, being:
Collaboration	3 studies
Voting	2 studies

Table 2. Game design elements employed by the included studies

Based on the available literature, it can be concluded that the majority of studies in this field were empirical in nature, as only two studies provided a detailed description of their *conceptual* design. Out of the 18 *empirical* studies, 10 were purely quantitative, two were qualitative, and six used a combination of these two methods. Half of the empirical studies were *controlled experiments*, in which five used between-subjects factorial design, either to analyse the use of stereotypical-male, stereotypical-female, and control versions of a gamified

platform, to understand the usage of gamification by women and men across three different semester, or to evaluate the effects of gamified or non-gamified platforms on two age groups (60 to 69 years old and 70 to 79 years old). The other four controlled experiments employed a between-subjects design to compare gamification to non-gamified platforms. The nine remaining empirical investigations were conducted using either single-case or multiple-case studies, as summarised in Table 3.

Nature	20 studies, being:
Conceptual	2 studies
Empirical	18 studies
Empirical approach	18 studies, being:
Factorial controlled experiment	5 studies
Between-group controlled experiment	4 studies
Single case studies	7 studies
Multiple case studies	2 studies
Data collection	18 studies, being:
Questionnaires	17 studies
Interaction logs	8 studies
Pre- and post- tests	5 studies
Focus groups	2 studies
Interviews	1 study
Data analysis	18 studies, being:
Descriptive statistics	12 studies
Inferential statistics	12 studies
Thematic analysis	6 studies
Content analysis	3 studies

Table 3. Overview of research methods employed by the included studies

The predominant data collection methods were *questionnaires* (17 studies) and *interaction logs* (8 studies). Data collection included the use of validated instruments, such as the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), Rating Scale Mental Effort (RSME), Flow State Scale (FSS), and System Usability Scale (SUS). Considering that the majority of research employed quantitative and mixed methodologies, the data analysis was primarily done through descriptive and inferential statistics, including t-tests, ANOVA, and Pearson's correlation.

4.3 EFFECTS (RQ3)

In relation to measured outcomes, nearly all studies assessed psychological results (i.e., 17 out of 18 empirical studies) of gamification, including *experience* and *perceived effort* (4 studies each), *attitude* and *motivation* (3 studies each), *anxiety levels*, *flow state* and *interest* (2 studies each), and *aggressiveness* and *enjoyment* (1 study each). Meanwhile, 12 studies investigated behavioural outcomes, especially focusing on *performance* (7 studies) and *participation* (4 studies).

In terms of the effects of such measurements, three studies reported a better *experience* in teachers, seniors, and students using gamification related to EDI, but one study identified no changes on the travel experience of individuals with visual impairment. Two studies revealed lower levels of *perceived effort* among South Africans and parents, whereas one study identified no significant effects on older adults and another study reported that men exhibited higher effort levels in certain functionalities. Three studies identified positive changes in the *attitude* of students, parents and older adults. Three studies examined *motivation*, but only two of them were able to identify any changes, specifically noticing a significant rise among students and content creators. Concerning *anxiety levels*, one study reported a reduction in anxiety among refugee children, while the other found an elevation in anxiety among women who used gamification that reinforced male stereotypes. The gender-stereotyped gamification did not influence the *flow state* in one study, whereas the second study in this same platform reported that the version that portrayed women in a stereotypical manner resulted in an increase in the flow state. In terms of *interest*, one study observed a rise in participants' exploration of content in languages that have limited resources. On the other hand, another study found that girls were initially less inclined than boys to show an interest in computer science, while these same girls demonstrated a more substantial increase in interest than boys when it came to learning about careers in digital forensics and cybersecurity. One study observed a noticeable increase in *aggressiveness* among individuals who used gamification with male stereotypes. Another study found that women reported higher levels of *enjoyment* when badges, points, and leaderboards were used, while men preferred points and leaderboards. Seven studies documented improved behavioural outcomes, as evidenced by increased *performance* in five of them, whereas there was no significant difference in the other two. Four studies also examined the impact of *participation*, being positively related to learning and reduced

alcohol consumption. However, participation had no effect on antiretroviral therapy uptake or adherence. Additionally, participation was found to be negatively associated with age, meaning that older adults were less likely to participate in a gamified platform. A summary of these effects can be found in Table 4.

Metric	Effect		
	Decrease	Neutral	Increase
Experience		1	3
Effort in use	2	1	1
Attitude			3
Motivation		1	2
Anxiety	1		1
Flow		1	1
Interest		1	2
Aggressiveness			1
Enjoyment			1
Identification			1
Playfulness	1		
Behavioural	Decrease	Neutral	Increase
Performance		2	5
Participation	1	2	2

Table 4. Effects identified by the included studies

5. Discussion

This study aimed to examine the contexts (RQ1), approaches (RQ2), and effects (RQ3) of gamification in relation to or based on EDI. These findings provide a thorough understanding of how gamification can effectively promote EDI, as well as shed light on the potential for gamification to become more equitable, diverse, and inclusive. Additionally, the findings identify areas that require further attention and improvement in future research.

In response to RQ1, gamification is both a means and a subject of EDI. Gamified EDI directly tackled issues related to gender, age, language, sexual orientation, disability, and immigration status. Similarly, gamification, as a discipline alongside EDI, focuses on addressing the specific effects of motivational affordances related to gender, age, and disability. In addition to identifying the populations that are currently being examined in the literature, our research also sheds light on additional marginalised groups that are not being addressed, such as those based on race, ethnicity, and socioeconomic position. Gamification in EDI has primarily focused on addressing gender disparities in STEM education (which are fields that are predominantly dominated by men) as well as improving healthcare services for marginalised groups. However, we still observe a lack of research in several contexts that are prevalent in our daily lives, such as corporate training and social media (BUTLER et al., 2024).

In response to RQ2, the intersection between gamification and EDI by several psychological, game design, and pedagogical theories. The majority of game elements implemented by the studies followed the trend from overall gamification studies and were centred around the sense of achievement (e.g., points, leaderboards, and badges), with a limited number of elements related to immersion and social interaction, despite EDI being essentially social in nature. This result emphasises that social dimensions have not yet been fully incorporated into the implementation of gamification in relation to EDI. Studies were mostly empirical, involving data collection through techniques such as questionnaires and interaction logs. These studies also employed rigorous procedures such as controlled experiments and case studies to ensure the reliability and validity of their findings. However, since the studies mostly focused on quantitative analysis, they offered a quantifiable comprehension of individuals' preferences and requirements but might have missed some in-depth insights into the mechanisms and rationales behind how gamification contributes to and aligns with EDI initiatives. Still, rigorous quantitative studies are supported towards advancing, especially if run on a large-scale, to allow testing the current knowledge more intensively and precisely.

In response to RQ3, gamification in conjunction with EDI actions has shown potential in promoting both psychological and behavioural transformation. Most research has shown that people from varied backgrounds had a favourable experience and improved performance while participating in gamification. Nevertheless, the evaluation of exertion in utilisation and involvement produced more varied outcomes, highlighting the intricacy of the interaction between gamification and EDI and its subtle influence on various individuals and situations. Although it is yet too early to definitively prove the long-term good impacts of gamification, the noticeable benefits it has shown thus far are significant and cannot be ignored. These findings give a promising basis for continued investigation and improvement in this area.

While research on this topic has shown promising early momentum, we have yet to achieve gamified EDI as a unified discipline. Addressing some of the identified gaps in the literature, we would encourage future research to investigate underrepresented diversity dimensions (e.g., ethnicity and socioeconomic level) to better understand their experiences and provide agency towards emancipation and in more diverse contexts (e.g., business and social work), while also supporting dominant groups in becoming aware, questioning, and upholding equitable rights within existing power structures through gamification. Moreover, future work should balance the types of game element types to suit diverse people (i.e., inclusive gamification that considers individual needs) and contexts (e.g., facilitating perspective-taking through immersion, strengthening community-building through social interaction). Considering gamification as a cultural and societal development, future work should consider studies that go beyond academic publications and include grey to be able to grasp a more comprehensive picture of the use of gamification towards and alongside EDI. Finally, future work should also consider different means through which gamification and other forms of entertainment (e.g., theatres, sports, music) could support and contribute to EDI actions, being studied, recognised and evaluated by academic researchers and agencies.

6. Conclusion

This review describes the EDI purposes being tackled by gamification and to whom these gamified interventions were designed for, the core game design principles used, and the main results achieved by the intersection of gamification and EDI thus far, as well as current limitations to be addressed by our own work during GAMEHEARTS and by any future work on this topic. These results and implications support the upcoming development and evaluation tasks of the impact of video games in shaping a more inclusive society (WP5) in GAMEHEARTS.

Still, we must acknowledge the limitations of this work. In our best efforts to define the search approach, we did not include some relevant keywords (such as diversified, prejudice, justice, and intersectionality) because they did not yield any new records in extensive search tests conducted throughout the protocol definition. Moreover, we also understand that gamification as an umbrella term for any development in which reality becomes more gameful might not be universal and keywords such as games, gameful, game-based, and play could have been used to promote a more comprehensive picture of the literature. In the same way, our search engines followed the most used ones in the gamification field, but literature reviews are not commonly used in EDI. Therefore, it is possible that there are significant terms and search engines that have been inadvertently overlooked, which could result in varying outcomes. We acknowledge that our selection criteria may have perpetuated obstacles stemming from dominant power structures, particularly in relation to language and accessibility. By exclusively considering records published in English, we disregarded 139 studies that could have yielded more representative and less colonising results. In addition, we refrained from reaching out to the authors of the 50 records that were not available to us, even though we attempted to locate these records through alternative legitimate channels such as ResearchGate and Academia.edu. Throughout this research, we attempted to maintain a neutral stance, while acknowledging that individuals are inevitably influenced by unconscious biases that impact their decision-making.

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8. Appendix A: List of Included Studies

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